

Researchers' experiences of publishing academic books open access

Case studies on open access publishing

These case studies are produced by Insights Media for UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The case studies are the outcome of interviews with the researchers who participated in the project. The interviews were conducted in 2024. The views in these case studies are those of the researchers and do not necessarily reflect the views, priorities, and policies of UKRI.

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This is version 3 of this document. This version includes updates to the Index and a correction on page 45.

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Janneke Adema, Associate Professor in Digital Media at The Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University

Driving experimentation

– Janneke Adema

Publishing books open access increases the visibility of research and researchers. It also enables academia to be more creative and to experiment with how research outputs are communicated.

Publishing open access is a natural choice for Janneke Adema. Associate Professor in Digital Media at The Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University, she has always worked openly. And she has been advocating for change in how and where research is published for many years.

Breaking down barriers

Adema says there shouldn't be any barriers to accessing research. Nor does she believe in waiting to put a finished product out there. When it's suitable and appropriate, she believes in open practice throughout the research lifecycle, from the initial conception of a research idea and the planning stages, data collection and sourcing information, through to analysis and publication. An early blogger, she has regularly invited others to collaborate with her and engage with her work as it progresses. She explained:

“ Communicating my research openly is something I've always done, right from the start of my academic career. I've always put as much as possible on my blog and shared it – my work in progress, my research presentations, my conference presentations and my papers.

Benefiting from working openly

This highly visible and transparent approach has worked well for Adema. It enabled her to create a buzz around her work early on in her career, raising her profile and getting her noticed in academic circles.

She said:

“Being an early adopter of publishing openly has been very beneficial to my career - it meant I made connections with more senior colleagues.”

Publishing openly has given Adema a much bigger, broader reach. It has also made it easier for her research to be used and explored in education settings and in reading groups.

Experimental publishing

Adema thinks open access isn't just about access to research - it breaks down other barriers, such as how research is created and presented. Her work is often processual and multi-modal, with her open access book – Living Books: Experiments in the Posthumanities - being available in several forms. Published by the MIT Press, there is a print, a PDF, and an online version, which can be further updated and commented on. The online version is published on the PubPub platform, hosted by Knowledge Futures, an independent nonprofit organisation founded by the MIT Press and the MIT Media Lab.

Adema wants people to interact with her work, encouraging them to add comments and make annotations and reuse her work in different contexts. She explained:

“ Having more multi-modal, experimental connections around the book has been crucial to the work that I'm doing and the kind of scholarship that I'm arguing for. We need to get books out of their containers.

Alternative, more ethical publishing models

Adema would like to see a community-led, not-for-profit publishing ecosystem thrive. She works with several small, not-for-profit publishers, academics and other people working in scholarly communications who have developed models to publish books without paywalls for readers or charges to authors.

She thinks moving to a different publishing system would enable more experimental forms of publishing to flourish. But, she says there are cultural barriers that need to come down, particularly for early career researchers, who can find it hard to challenge established norms.

Adema said:

“As researchers we’re accustomed to this idea that we’re lucky to get published and we can’t make any demands. It’s hard, particularly as an early career researcher, to push back against that. But you can and there are always options.”

She says community-led presses are often more open to new forms of publishing. Some of them specifically want to help early career scholars, so she advises those starting out in academia to seek them out.

Gwyn Bevan, Emeritus
Professor of Policy Analysis in
the Department of
Management, London School of
Economics and Political
Science

Open access books: a modern way of publishing

– Gwyn Bevan

Technology enhances research. It enables academics to work and publish openly, access more material and more quickly, and reach a wider audience.

The research landscape has changed dramatically during Gwyn Bevan's time in academia, including how and where academics publish and why. Bevan, Emeritus Professor of Policy Analysis in the Department of Management at the London School of Economics and Political Science, welcomes those changes. He says the benefits are immense – to academics, to research, to academia and to society more generally.

How research used to happen

Bevan published his first book in 1980, on healthcare. Back then, academics had to buy books to access research or travel to libraries.

He said:

“If you wanted to get an article, you'd have to go to a library and photocopy it. It was a very laborious process.”

Digitisation changes everything

With the advent of the Internet, digitisation and more latterly, open access publishing, Bevan says everything has become a lot simpler and a lot quicker. And academics can draw on more material than ever before.

He added:

“So much is available electronically now – it’s transformational. You’re able to get access to original documents, including documents published in the early 20th century.”

Publishing today

Bevan recently published his first book open access with LSE Press – How Did Britain Come to This? His university advised publishing open access and met the publishing costs. Bevan has been delighted at the attention it has received, having notched up over 3000 downloads in the first nine months.

This experience has led Bevan to conclude that academics who publish open access gain far more visibility for themselves and their work, boosting their profile and impact. He believes making research freely and easily available will lead to higher readership numbers and higher citation numbers. He said:

“ What happens is that stuff you can access electronically will get read and cited, and stuff which you have to buy as a book or go to a library or access behind a paywall, will not do anywhere near as well and will not have the same reach or citations.

How was publishing open access different?

Bevan discovered that the process was very similar to traditional publishing, although he did have to spend a lot of time including links and checking that they worked. Although it was time consuming, Bevan said it was worth the effort because links are useful, making research outputs stronger. And on the flip side, having an electronic publication meant there was no need for him to provide an index because of all the links.

Taking research beyond academia

Bevan's book discusses governance in the UK, exploring the current state of public services, neoliberalism, privatisation, housing, healthcare and so on. The book was not written for the benefit of Bevan's academic colleagues - they are not his target audience. He wanted to write a book that appealed to everyone, particularly people outside of academia. The idea was to make academic principles and concepts accessible to the general public, both through publishing open access and through clear, jargon-free content.

**Francesca Coppa,
Professor of
English, Theatre
and Film Studies,
Muhlenberg College**

Open access helps new voices be heard

– Francesca Coppa

Open access helps academics think differently – about how research outputs like books are created and shared, and how different voices are surfaced and represented

Open access publishing encourages diversity and inclusivity. This is very important to Francesca Coppa, Professor of English, Theatre and Film Studies at Muhlenberg College in the US.

Openness and transparency

One of the founders of the Organization for Transformative Works (OTW), an initiative that started as the largest all female open source coding project on the Internet, Coppa has always experimented with new, open ways of working. OTW is all about open culture and open access and it has been very successful – one of its projects, The Archive of Our Own, is a popular global entertainment website, according to Coppa.

She said:

“Through publishing open access, the Internet is not only a place of commerce, but a place of making and sharing good information and art.”

Remix cultures

Coppa is a strong advocate and lobbyist for remix cultures, for fair use practices and for less restrictive copyright. Her most recent book *Vidding: A History* focuses on fan-made videos. She was determined it would be available not just to academics but also to the community of artists the book is centred around and to any other interested parties, especially students, who she believes need to see a more diverse array of artists. The book explores a grassroots feminist art form of people making videos and sharing them freely, so it was inconceivable to Coppa that it would go behind a paywall.

Enabling new forms of creative expression

If Coppa's book had been published within the standard confines of academic publishing, Coppa says it wouldn't have worked.

Her scholarship focuses on transmedia storytelling, exploring the interplay between text, theatre, video and image. It was vital that her research output reflected that - the online version is multimedia, including 150 videos, clips, images and links. Those videos, clips, images and links are integral to the research and Coppa's exploration of vidding. They also make for much more dynamic, useful materials in a teaching context.

This was only possible because the digital format enabled the content to be embedded within the book. But hosting so many videos was expensive. Fortunately for Coppa, her college was very supportive and helped her apply for grants to cover those costs.

Coppa also has good connections in the transmedia storytelling community so getting permissions to host content was quite straightforward. But she says a culture of fair use in the US and fair dealing in the UK is important to enable an open access culture to flourish.

Finding the right publisher

When choosing a publisher, Coppa says academics need to look around to establish the options available. She recommends talking to university librarians as they are

often extremely knowledgeable about which presses have strong support for open access. They may also have suggestions about how to obtain grants or funding.

If an academic wants to experiment with form and content, as Coppa has done, she says they need to be prepared to lead the conversation and find out what is possible. She said:

“ There are many resources for open access book publishing if a scholar thinks to ask the question. This can also be a conversation you have with an acquiring editor.

Bringing research into the classroom

There is a whole section in Coppa’s book dedicated to teachers. It is important to Coppa that teachers can use material that is of interest to them and share it flexibly with students as a link or transfer it to a smartboard in the classroom.

She thinks open access and open source hugely benefit underrepresented communities, enabling fresh voices and fresh perspectives to be heard.

She said:

“I don’t want to have any more barriers to people bringing diverse work into the classroom than there already are. It’s an inclusivity issue – that’s how you get the voices of people who are not mainstream artists into the classroom.”

Making scholarship visible and accessible

Coppa thinks the academic community needs to be realistic about how people access knowledge and information today. If research is out of reach, behind a paywall or in an expensive book, then many people will read and reference what they find freely through search engines. This has the effect of reducing the impact of individual research and individual authors and reducing the dissemination of scholarly findings.

But if research is freely available, then people find it and read it, as Coppa has found.

She said:

“People are citing it and using it and teaching it, which is what I wanted.”

**Martin Paul Eve,
Professor of Literature,
Technology and
Publishing, Birkbeck,
University of London**

Sharing research, not hoarding it

– Martin Eve

Open access to books enables more people to access and contribute to research. It encourages diversity of voices and thinking. And it makes the world a more equitable, knowledgeable place.

Knowledge and research should be at our fingertips. So says Martin Paul Eve, Professor of Literature, Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London. The technology exists to make research easily and freely available, but there are barriers that prevent it from happening on a wide scale.

Barriers to access

As someone with lived experience of access barriers – Eve has significant health and mobility issues which make it difficult for him to travel to libraries – Eve knows what a difference it makes when research is available digitally, free of cost.

Open access removes barriers. This doesn't just benefit people with disabilities. It benefits other people who also struggle to travel to libraries, such as those with caring responsibilities or financial constraints.

When access is denied, it impacts on individuals and the dissemination of research, says Eve.

He added:

“Knowledge doesn’t benefit anyone if it’s inaccessible. If things were openly accessible on the Internet, my life in research terms would be so much better.”

The North-South divide

Even many libraries can’t afford to pay for expensive books or subscription costs. This is particularly true of libraries in the Global South. Eve says this disadvantages scholars in places such as Africa.

Eve explained:

“Their work has been massively hindered by the fact they can’t get access to the same resources, but they’re still held to exactly the same standards of scholarship as everybody else. It also means research generally has less diversity and breadth of thinking.”

Good access improves research

When academics can access a diverse range of materials, it encourages speculative reading and the deeper exploration of ideas. It also facilitates scholarly ways of working. Eve said:

“ The easier you make it to check what someone has said and how they’re using a reference, the more inclined people will be to do it and the more rigorous their scholarly practices will end up being. Research is not finding or having access to material. It’s reading it, engaging with it, synthesising it and building on it.

Open access also fosters experimentation, inviting people to explore different outputs with their own research or other people’s – new formats, interactive elements and translation, for example.

The fear factor

Fear holds a lot of people back. Many academics view open access books as less prestigious and less impactful.

Eve says it couldn’t be further from the truth. He was awarded the Philip Leverhulme Prize for Literary Studies in 2019 and put that money into publishing his work open access. Without the prize, publishing open access would have been a lot harder for Eve as his university does not have the funds to give grants very easily. He has

published 10 books open access and has very high citation figures and a very high profile. He said:

“ It’s had a very positive impact on my career. And I have much greater satisfaction and purpose in what I do, knowing there’s a much broader audience for my work. People who don’t engage with open access are missing out on a huge opportunity to do good in the world.

Over time, Eve thinks more and more academics will switch to open access, when they realise it will improve their reader and citation numbers. While those who close themselves off only reach a limited audience, diminishing their impact.

**Jean-Paul Faguet,
Professor of the
Political Economy of
Development, London
School of Economics
and Political Science**

Publicly funded research should be publicly available

– Jean Paul Faguet

Academic research is publicly funded so should be freely available to the public. It is particularly important that research is available to people and institutions that would benefit from it.

An increasing number of academics are advocating for open access publishing. They think people across the world – fellow academics, but also society in general – should have equal access to research and knowledge.

Jean-Paul Faguet, Professor of the Political Economy of Development at London School of Economics and Political Science and a Fellow of the Academy of Social Sciences, feels very strongly about this, not least because his work involves countries where access to research is currently very limited.

Where access is denied

Faguet says his many of his peers in institutions in countries such as Africa and Latin America are denied access to research, particularly research coming out of the most prestigious and influential publishers. He says research and knowledge should be freely available to everybody who wants and needs it, particularly if the research is about them and their country.

He recently co-authored an open access monograph called *Decentralised Governance: Crafting Effective Democracies Around the World*. Published by LSE

Press, it involved 23 academics. They chose LSE Press because it offered open access. Faguet said:

“ Open access is, for all of us, a really big deal. The people we study live in developing countries, and the results, conclusions and recommendations – the main point of this research – is really aimed at developing countries, first and foremost. We can’t go and get data and experience from developing countries and then lock it up behind a paywall where they can’t see it.

Paying twice for research

There is another reason why Faguet advocates for open access. Academics are paid to conduct research so he thinks it is wrong that anyone – person or institution - should have to pay again to access that research.

He explains:

“I just don’t think it’s right that the public has to pay twice. By funding our research grants and paying our salaries, they already paid to produce the research. Why should anyone have to pay again, just because it has been put behind a paywall?”

Faguet said he and his co-authors are all committed to the same principles – making the research freely available, rather than it going to a select few and publishers making money from it. The publisher waived costs that could not be covered by grants or other open access funding.

Open access benefits research

By publishing open access, Faguet says research reaches a far bigger, wider audience. This means it has more impact. Firstly, because people can access it and secondly because they can then act on it. He said:

“ A book published with a normal press is going to make it into a fraction of the world’s university libraries. We got our first citation within a day of publication, which never happens.

Faguet says there was also more flexibility about what was included in the monograph and how content could be presented. He and his fellow authors were able to include many more charts, graphs and illustrations than is customary in traditional publishing. This is a very useful, important consideration when producing a monograph about economics, where charts and graphs are a key way of demonstrating findings.

**Aileen Fyfe, Professor
of Modern History,
University of St
Andrews**

Senior scholars to drive open access for books

– Aileen Fyfe

It is time for senior scholars to embrace open access publishing for books – demonstrating that it's just as credible, just as scholarly, and will lead to more readers, a wider variety of readers and a stronger profile.

Aileen Fyfe, Professor of Modern History at the University of St Andrews, published her first open access book in 2022, in collaboration with three postdoc researchers. *A History of Scientific Journals*, it wasn't initially conceived as an open access publication, but three things changed Fyfe's mind.

The switch to open access

Soon after Fyfe started the AHRC-funded research in 2013, looking at the history of academic publishing from the 17th century to the present day (including open access), she signed with an established press. But, given the nature of the topic, it felt increasingly odd to not move with the times and publish openly.

The book was also long, far longer than traditional presses like – at one point, Fyfe was told it might have to be split into three volumes.

She explained:

“We didn't want to do that, because it would be the sort of thing that's priced at £300, sits on library shelves in perhaps 200 locations around the world... and nobody ever reads it! We wanted people to read our book.”

Nor could they trim the wordcount – the book is a chronological history spanning 350 years, so there was a lot of important information to explore to do the topic justice.

Switching mindset

The biggest hurdle, however, was the fear factor. As an established scholar, Fyfe was happy to go open access, but she was concerned it might damage the career prospects of the postdoc researchers she was working with. But, one of the postdoc researchers was a strong advocate for open access and persuaded her otherwise.

Fyfe said:

“Her confidence in it enabled me to feel that I wouldn’t be doing a bad thing by the postdoc researchers if we went ahead with open access.”

So Fyfe switched to an open access publisher who didn’t place any restrictions on the length of the book or the number of illustrations it contained.

Open access = more readers

Going open access has led to a much larger and diverse readership and greater visibility for Fyfe and her researchers. As soon as the book was published, it started clocking up views – 1,800 downloads in the first month. In comparison, Fyfe’s previous best-selling book totalled just 865 sales in more than 15 years.

Fyfe says the fact it is easily and freely available makes a huge difference, and in many ways. She explained:

“ I can give a talk, put the link up and know that people in the audience will be clicking on the link right away and having a look. And it’s so easy for the link to be shared online. This has made our book visible to many more people, including people who aren’t historians, but are interested in the contemporary challenges of academic publishing.

And one of the postdoc researchers has since published her second open access book.

Born digital

Fyfe also likes the fact that open access publishers think digitally – books are born digital. This breaks down traditional barriers around pagination, the number of illustrations, the form the output takes, etc.

She said:

“There’s a flexibility that lets you produce a product that fits the project you’re doing. You can experiment more.”

The role of senior academics

It was a postdoc who convinced Fyfe to switch to open access, but Fyfe thinks senior academics should be leading the charge. She said:

“ Change has to come from more established scholars. We need to see senior members of the profession speaking out in favour, demonstrating that it can be done and that the publishing process is very similar in terms of editorial boards, peer review, copy editing etc. And that it’s not an inferior product, either intellectually or as a reading experience.

Fyfe says there are several myths about open access that need debunking – such as that it will damage people’s careers because publishing open access is less prestigious than traditional publishing – and that senior members of the academic community need to get on board and demonstrate otherwise.

**Dr Ellie Gore, Lecturer in
Global Political Economy
in the Department of
Politics, University of
Manchester**

Open access publishing in and beyond the Global North

– Elie Gore

Publishing academic books open access can make research available to a truly global audience.

Academics in the Global South are structurally disadvantaged compared to academics in the Global North. Paywalls, the cost of academic books, and other barriers to accessing resources exacerbate longstanding material and epistemological inequalities between institutions and academics in the Global North and those in the Global South.

Queer politics and activism in Ghana

Dr Ellie Gore, Lecturer in Global Political Economy in the Department of Politics, University of Manchester, has written their first open access book. Entitled *Between HIV Prevention and LGBTI Rights: The Political Economy of Queer Activism in Ghana*, the book is based on ethnographic research conducted with LGBTI/HIV activists and organisations in Ghana. It's an emerging area of academic research and Gore says it was important that the book was made available to as wide an audience as possible, both to have maximum impact and for ethical reasons.

They added:

“I’m hoping it’s not just academics and researchers that read it. I’d like to think it is of interest to policymakers, activists, civil society organisations in Africa and around

the world who are concerned about LGBTI rights and the struggle for queer liberation.”

A Ghanaian audience

Above all, Gore wants their research to be available to their colleagues and other stakeholders in Ghana, including everyone who participated in the fieldwork. Had they not gone open access, it would have been difficult for most people in Ghana to access the book.

Gore says this has happened time and time again. They explained:

“ Research conducted in parts of the Global South, and in Africa in particular, can be very extractive. Academics from the Global North go there, get their data, then write their publications – and who gets to read them? This is one small way of trying to mitigate that extractive dynamic.

Who produces knowledge about Africa?

Gore thinks that a lot more needs to be done to ensure that academics, activists, and other voices from across Africa can push back against the discourses and narratives created by the Global North about the continent. Indeed, as a British academic, Gore wasn't sure if they should write their book at all. Ultimately, they hoped that by publishing their findings and putting the voices and experiences of queer Ghanaian activists centre stage, the book might make a small but valuable contribution to understanding queer politics in West Africa.

Gore's experience of publishing open access

As an academic based at the University of Manchester, publishing open access was easier than Gore had expected.

They said:

“I had thought it might be difficult to publish open access, but it turned out there were a few possible routes available to me.”

The University of Manchester runs an Open Access monograph competition, whereby the university's library pays the publishing costs, so that was one potential route. The other option was the UKRI's longform open access central fund. As

Gore's research was funded by an ERSC doctoral scholarship and an ESRC postdoctoral fellowship, they went for the latter option.

Open access – good and bad

While Gore thinks that open access can help address issues in who has access to knowledge, they are concerned about ongoing inequalities in who can publish their research and therefore whose knowledge and contribution is privileged and valued. African and Ghanaian ways of knowing are still often marginalised at best, if not excluded altogether.

They explained:

“If you are a Ghanaian academic working in a Ghanaian university, you are unlikely to have the resources or means to publish something open access.”

Gore says there needs to be a more radical and transformative approach to tackling the extractive logics and unequal power relations built into current academic research and publishing models.

**Roger Kain, Professor
of Humanities, School
of Advanced Study,
University of London**

Open access book publishing gains momentum

– Roger Kain

Up and coming academics will help create the change needed for open access publishing to gain wider acceptance

Early career researchers in the humanities may still be advised to publish with a traditional press, at least for their first book to help them gain tenure. But attitudes are changing as the academic community realises that open access can result in higher reader numbers, higher citations and more impact.

The next generation will drive change/generational differences

Roger Kain, Professor of Humanities at the School of Advanced Study, University of London, says a big hurdle that needs to be overcome is that senior managers in universities can still lack awareness of open access book publishing. Some view it as self-publishing and therefore of lower quality than traditional publishing. Kain refutes that, saying that open access books usually undergo the same rigorous scholarly processes, such as peer reviews and copy editing.

However, he thinks generational shifts will lead to cultural change.

He said:

“The generation of researchers who were early career five or so years ago and are now coming through to the mid-career stage – they are going to carry a very different view of open access to people of my generation.”

Kain's own experience of open access publishing

Kain is involved in a long-term project with the University of Chicago Press. It's a significant project – a global history of maps and mapping - spanning almost fifty years, multiple authors and more than twenty rounds of public funding. A while ago, Kain says the decision was made to make the research freely available, three years after publication for new books, immediately for those already published.

He said:

“We had started to get comments – ‘is it good that all this public money is put into these wonderful books, this wonderful research, but then it's locked away behind a paywall?’”

Impact of open access publishing

One of the most obvious benefits to open access publishing is higher reader numbers. Kain says there had been 5.6 million hits on the project last time he looked. Some of them have been educators, downloading material and circulating it to students, so Kain is pleased it is being used pedagogically. There has also been an uptick in sales of the printed books since the project went open access.

Fairer access to research and increased collaboration

There are two other major benefits to open access book publishing. It disseminates knowledge and research more widely, making academia more equitable globally. It also encourages academic discourse around research, again on a global level.

Kain said:

“It facilitates conversations around the world. And it breaks down some of the haves and have-nots barriers.”

The use of third party material

That's not to say that open access publishing is without its challenges. Authors regularly encounter problems around images and consent to use third party material. This has been particularly problematic for the project Kain is involved with as there are many, many illustrations in the books – about 1,000 per book.

Kain estimates that for the majority of the images in his book, it was a straightforward process - most libraries and private owners were happy to waive permission costs. Some others asked for a PDF copy of the printed image or a complimentary copy of the hardback book, which retails at \$500 a book. For some, negotiations were more complex, involving detailed licence agreements.

All of this added a lot of time and cost to the project, not least from an administrative perspective. Permission costs were largely covered by private donations; it is common practice in the US for federal dollars to be matched by private dollars.

But, Kain says all the hassle was to be expected for books with so many images. He has no regrets that the decision was made to publish open access, albeit with a delay for the latest volumes.

**Geoffrey Khan, Regius
Professor of Hebrew,
University
of Cambridge**

Open access means actual dissemination

– Geoffrey Khan

Publishing books open access helps academics reach a broader, more diverse audience that includes the Global South and the general public.

Book publishing enables academics to disseminate their findings far and wide. Or so they hope. Many find their readership is actually quite limited due to the prohibitively high cost of hardback academic books and library subscription fees.

Geoffrey Khan is Regius Professor of Hebrew at the University of Cambridge, and general editor of the open access series Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures published by Open Book Publishers. His first books were published through traditional presses, and he was disappointed to realise how few copies sold.

He said:

“I was getting more and more frustrated with the lack of dissemination of the books. Disseminating academic research creates impact and publication is supposed to mean dissemination, but I wasn’t achieving that with traditional publishers.”

The switch to open access

Khan also realised that the cost of books and library subscriptions means that only wealthy universities – largely universities in the western world – can afford to buy books and access knowledge. As a result, many universities and academics are denied access to important research.

He decided to do something about it, setting up an open access series in his field. He began with his own book – The Tiberian Pronunciation Tradition of Biblical Hebrew, which won the 2021 Frank Moore Cross Book Award. Published open access about three years ago, take-up has been far greater than any of his previous works. Citations have also been far higher. Khan said:

“ It rapidly became clear that an incredible number of downloads were taking place, all over the world. The free on demand PDF was the big feature. So far it has been downloaded nearly 16,000 times. I sold under 100 books with my previous book.

Reaching a broader audience

Khan’s readership has also extended out of the Global North into the Global South. He is delighted that academics in less wealthy countries and institutions now have access. And to discover that the general public is also interested in his research.

He said:

“There is a genuine thirst for access to scholarship, a hunger for knowledge which goes beyond academic institutions. Academics have an important role to play in that, rather than being locked away in ivory towers.”

Preserving endangered languages and cultures

Some of the books in Khan’s series feature endangered languages and cultures, involving minority communities that have been displaced. Producing the research and disseminating it open access helps to preserve those languages and cultures and ensures that the communities where the research was conducted can have access to the research outcome.

Khan explains:

“It’s absolutely essential for these communities to get access to the documentation. Typically, in the past, scholars would do fieldwork in living communities and then publish an expensive book through traditional publishers, and no members of the community could afford to buy.”

Financing open access

Funding is a major challenge for the series. It's a not-for-profit initiative, but it does need to generate funds as many authors can't afford to pay to publish. Khan believes there should be many more initiatives like this – series run by academics in their field – but that there needs to be a way to secure regular funding beyond one-off grants and trust funds.

Khan set up a partnership between his university department and the not-for-profit open access publisher Open Book Publishers. Financial support for the series comes from various sources, including departmental trust funds, donations raised by Khan, grants of authors, and the open access library support scheme administered by Open Book Publishers. Compared to team-based research grants, the costs are relatively low. The series could be funded for 20 years or more for the average cost of a four-year team-based research project.

**Professor Marie Lall,
Chair of Education and
South Asian Studies,
UCL Institute of
Education**

Publishing open access drives access, impact and profile

– Marie Lall

Publishing open access enables Marie Lall to disseminate research more widely and reach her target audience in the Global South.

Open access fosters global knowledge creation and dissemination. It makes research more accessible, equitable and impactful. So says Professor Marie Lall, Chair of Education and South Asian Studies at the UCL Institute of Education. Lall currently focuses on the role of education as a safe space for students who are forced migrants, due to conflict or climate change.

Education reforms in Myanmar

Lall says it was particularly important that her most recent book – Myanmar’s Education Reforms. A pathway to social justice? - was open access so that people in Myanmar could access it. That would not have been possible with traditional publishing. Lall chose UCL Press because it was open access and the publishing fees were waived.

She said:

“Myanmar has had a coup. Nobody can go to a bookshop, nor do they think to spend money on a book, but they will click on a link and read it.”

The Myanmar book had been downloaded 37,724 times in 173 countries by July 2024, with 2,793 of those downloads being in Myanmar. She says the physical version could not achieve anywhere near those kinds of numbers.

She added:

“I would never have imagined selling over 37,000 copies of my book.”

Producing books people will read

Lall says she writes books so that people read them, giving her research a bigger audience. If she publishes the traditional route, it limits the number of people who can and will access her work. And it would definitely preclude her target audience, the Global South, including people involved in policy work, from accessing her research. Lall’s work has policy impact, which would be so much harder to achieve if it wasn’t open access.

Policy makers in the Global South have limited access to academic content that is published traditionally, as they often don’t have access to libraries or subscriptions.

Involving the local community

The majority of Lall’s work is field work, using data provided by people in the local community. Most of those people would not be able to access the research they contributed to without open access. She explained:

“ Open access has made all the difference. These people cannot buy the book or get hold of it and there’s no way I could send them copies. Open access takes that problem away. When it’s published, you just send the link to the community leads and they can download it or pass it on. Knowledge should be accessible to everyone.

Lall thinks that when the local community knows the research will be freely available to them it builds trust and makes it easier for her to ask for participation.

Making sure research has impact

Not only does Lall think publishing open access is a morally and socially responsible thing to do, she says it has also benefitted her career. Her work is more widely read, boosting her profile.

Lall acts as a mentor to junior researchers. When they ask her for advice about how and where to publish, Lall always advocates for open access. She likes co-authoring with junior researchers on open access projects, thinking it is a great way to help raise their profile. She said:

“ *When you start publishing, academics normally go to traditional publishers who charge £100 or more for a hardback and nobody buys it. It's only available in certain libraries. I say to academics 'Do yourself a long term favour - try to make your research read'.*

David Luke, Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa, London School of Economics and Political Science

Knowledge without boundaries

– David Luke

Publishing books open access enables academics to broaden the reach of their work, inform global debate and help shape policy.

David Luke wants his research to have impact and make a difference. To achieve that, the Professor in Practice and Strategic Director at the Firoz Lalji Institute for Africa at the London School of Economics and Political Science says research needs to get into the hands of people who need it and can use it. Publishing open access enables him to do that.

Sharing Knowledge

Luke thinks it is critically important that people across the globe have equal access to knowledge. He said:

“ I think research should be shared among scholars, among people who can use the research. I think being able to share research across boundaries is a great thing. It’s how knowledge can make a difference.

There is one audience in particular that Luke wants to reach with his research – an African audience. His latest book, published with LSE Press, is called *How Africa Trades*. He knows from experience how hard it is to get books and research to libraries and people who need it in Africa. He also knows what a difference it would make if that access barrier was removed.

Research as a lever for change

Anyone who is working to bring about change – policy makers, scholars, community groups and activists, for example – need access to insights, ideas and information as they emerge. Luke and his team of researchers have just finished a new book, called *How Africa Eats*. It too will be published open access and Luke hopes it will help drive change.

He explained:

“We are hoping this book will revive thinking about the urgency of dealing with problems of hunger. We thought new research could uncover where the bottlenecks are and give policy makers, activists and other people, new material for campaigning.”

Challenging assumptions

Luke says it is also important that new research is circulated in the Global North, to reframe the debate and stimulate thinking around current challenges and opportunities in Africa.

He said:

“Some of this work challenges assumptions in the Global North, so it’s also aimed at scholars, policy makers and others in the Global North.”

Benefits to academics

Publishing open access has had a positive impact on the careers of Luke and his co-authors, giving them and their work greater visibility. *How Africa Trades* won the BCA (Business Council for Africa) African Business Book of the Year Award 2024, with judges praising the fact the book was accessible, due to being open access. Luke has been invited to various events, including a visit to the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace in the US. And two of the researchers in his team have gone on to secure new, permanent posts.

Luke says having published open access also helps when reaching out for funding. Foundation and funding bodies like the fact the team have and continue to publish open access, that the research reaches a wide audience and is breaking down access barriers.

The future of publishing

Luke firmly believes that the academic community will embrace open access and that the funding costs will be built into grants. In Luke's case, the costs of publishing his books open access were waived because he is a researcher at LSE.

He said:

"This is the direction of travel. It's just a matter of time."

Dr Samuel Moore,
Scholarly
communications
specialist, Cambridge
University Library and an
early career researcher

Busting the myth that open access means lower quality

– Samuel Moore

Publishing books open access encourages innovation while retaining the rigorous processes and quality of traditional publishing.

Open access is just as high quality, just as scholarly as traditional publishing, but parts of academia still perceive it as less prestigious and less valid. As a result, many authors are advised against publishing open access, particularly those in the early stages of their career who are looking to make a name for themselves.

Advice from the top

Senior academics often recommend publishing through established presses as a better, safer way for fledgling academics to advance their careers and gain tenure.

This was the advice given to Dr Samuel Moore, a scholarly communications specialist at Cambridge University Library, who is early on in his career himself. Moore, who has a PhD in Digital Humanities, has already published two books open access and is soon to publish his first monograph - *Publishing Beyond the Market: Open Access, Care and the Commons* - through the University of Michigan Press.

Moore disputes the suggestion that open access is inferior in quality to traditional presses. He says it is all about perception and established norms, rather than reality. He said:

“ It’s completely untrue that open access books are of lower quality. Publishing open access felt to me like a traditional publishing experience in terms of copy editing, peer reviews and such like.

The emergence of scholar-led presses

Moore is one of the Radical Open Access Collective organisers, a community of scholar-led, not-for-profit presses, journals and other open access projects. He says open access facilitates community-led publishing, which he thinks is a very exciting, positive development.

“A lot of the presses that I like are scholar-led presses that are really embedded within their academic disciplines. Automatically, you have this quality to it, because it’s being not just submitted by an expert, it’s being shaped by an expert in the field, edited by one and sometimes even copy edited by one.”

Experimentation and innovation

Open access facilitates innovation, enabling academics to create and publish research in different formats. By advising early career researchers to stick with traditional publishing presses and methods, Moore thinks academia is missing the opportunity to explore new possibilities and new ways of reaching audiences. Moore explains:

“ We don’t just have to produce books that follow the standard book format. There are many other ways to present research – remixed books, for example. And you can incorporate sound and video.

Giving voice to early career researchers

As the next generation of academics emerges, Moore says they will have their own ideas about how to produce research and will want to experiment. He thinks those ideas should be encouraged and allowed to flourish.

“A while ago, Cambridge University Library hosted a workshop with early career researchers. All of them had these really amazing, in-depth ideas of what they would do if they were allowed to publish in a different way. We had presentations from people talking about using archives in interesting ways or using rapid publishing, for example.”

Attitudes are changing, but Moore thinks it will take time for perceptions of open access to fully change.

Joanna Page, Professor of Latin American Studies, Director of CRASSH, University of Cambridge

Open access breaks down barriers

– Joanna Page

Geography and wealth should not determine who has access to research and knowledge. Open access breaks down barriers, making research and knowledge available to all.

Knowledge should be democratised, freely available to people everywhere. That is what a lot of academics think. It's certainly what Joanna Page, Professor of Latin American Studies at the University of Cambridge, and Director of CRASSH (Centre for Research in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences) thinks. She said:

“ We need to think about what happens to knowledge globally. We should be aiming to create a system that is equitable on a global level.

Current barriers to access

Many academics, individuals, libraries and other institutions in Latin America struggle to access important research and knowledge because of the cost of academic books and subscription fees.

Page's research involves collaborating with academics and artists in Latin America, so for her, it is vital that they can access the research she produces. If she hadn't published open access, those academics and artists would have been denied

access to the research output. She thinks it would also have damaged her professional reputation in Latin American academic circles.

She said:

“There’s a very strong ground level feeling that scholarship should be accessible and free in Latin America.”

Greater reader numbers

Publishing open access has enabled Page to reach a much broader audience, in Latin America and beyond. When she posted her latest open access book on her social media channels, her Latin American collaborators picked it up and distributed it among their networks.

Page said:

“This really pushed it out to different markets. From what I’ve seen, individuals with large networks sharing on social media can be just as effective, if not more effective than the distribution processes of traditional presses.”

Quicker publication

Although the process was just as rigorous as with traditional publishing, and the output just as professional, Page says the open presses she has published with work in very agile ways. This has expedited publication times, which is important to Page because her work is on contemporary artists, so she likes her research to be available as quickly as possible.

Paying for open access

When Page first looked into publishing open access, it was easier to find a publisher that would foot the bill than she had expected. Some presses don’t advertise that they publish open access, while others are running pilot schemes or are prepared to waive fees on a case-by-case basis. Page says it’s important that academics look around and ask for opportunities.

But she is also concerned that the open access route could lead to new inequalities – rather than paying to access research, people will have to pay to publish it. And just as certain academics, particularly those in the Global South are less likely to

have the funds to access research, they are less likely to have the funds to pay to publish. Page said:

“ To create a more fully democratic access to knowledge across the world, we would also need to ensure that authors in other countries can not only read but also publish without having to pay.

**Matthew Reynolds,
Professor of English
and Comparative
Criticism, University
of Oxford**

Knowledge for everyone, everywhere

– Matthew Reynolds

Everyone everywhere should have access to research, but they don't. Open access publishing removes barriers, democratising access to knowledge.

There are several reasons why Matthew Reynolds decided to publish his book open access, the main one being his strong belief in the democratisation of knowledge.

The constraints of traditional publishing

Professor of English and Comparative Criticism at the University of Oxford, Reynolds says traditional academic publishing tends to be undemocratic. It keeps knowledge in an enclosed space, where only a privileged few – individuals and institutions who can afford expensive academic books or subscription fees – can access it.

Reynolds also thinks that traditional academic publishing tends to perpetuate established disciplinary structures and styles of writing. While these do have value, they can also hold back fresh thinking and restrict readership.

Breaking down barriers

Reynolds wants to break free from the traditional constraints of academic silos to produce more diverse and creative research outputs.

Literature, for example, doesn't belong in just one language or one location, he says. Interactions between different languages are a fundamental part of literary writing, but too often, literature is compartmentalised into national stories – English literature in the English department and Italian literature in the Italian department.

This is not people's lived experience of literature.

Literature transcending borders

Reynolds' latest book is called *Prismatic Jane Eyre: Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages*. Both the research and the open access costs for book were AHRC-funded. Many academics from around the world collaborated with him. He says literary interpretations are richer when different voices and perspectives are involved.

Reynolds explained:

“Charlotte Brontë's novel doesn't just exist in English. It's been translated more than 600 times into more than 68 languages. Reviewing all this work by translators and publishers in different locations is creative work. It's collaborative and creative, remaking and discovering new significances in new locations.”

Encouraging diversity of thinking and research

Publishing open access freed Reynolds from established publishing norms, enabling him to produce more experimental content, including digital interactive maps and verbal animations. He selected his publisher as it had a reputation for being innovative and were interested in the digital, interactive elements of the book.

Many of his co-authors are from different intellectual and linguistic traditions and use English in a variety of ways. It was important to him that they could write authentically, in a style that suited them, rather than having a prestige house style imposed on them. He wanted to move away from academic jargon and for lots of different languages and perspectives to be represented on the page.

Reynolds thinks this approach makes it easier to reach a more diverse audience, with different reference points and different experiences.

He explained:

“The work I do is about reaching people from different disciplinary silos. And my book is different from the traditional reading experience – I want people to explore it in ways that are interesting to them. I didn’t want it to be the sort of book that symbolises knowledge and configures readers as receivers of knowledge. I wanted it to be an interactive experience for them.”

Being an established academic, he was confident to be bold in his publishing decisions, but notes that if it had been his first book, it could have been a more challenging decision.

The benefit

The book was downloaded roughly 10,000 times in the first nine months, with 20% of those downloads coming from the Global South, which Reynolds is very pleased about. He said:

“ It seemed very necessary that what we wrote about be readily available to people in the Global South, in all the places where the book was translated, stopping the practice of academic work being extractive.

Reaching a wider, bigger audience has also boosted Reynolds’ profile, with him being asked to give lectures in the universities of Tunis, Shanghai Jiao Tong, Brown, Princeton, Dongguk (Seoul) and Lille, as well as Manchester, Leeds, East Anglia and Oxford Brookes. Had he not published open access, Reynolds think his book would not have generated the same level of interest and excitement.

New projects

Beyond this AHRC-funded project, Reynolds is working on other books. He is very keen to publish open access again, but says it is not always obvious how to achieve this. For one collaborative volume he has negotiated a Green open access agreement with a long-established publisher. However, another book may not be able to be published open access, as funding has not yet been secured to cover the costs.

**William Sutherland,
Professor of Conservation
Biology and Director of
Research, University of
Cambridge**

Open access means equitable access to research

– William Sutherland

Publishing books open access enables academics and conservationists across the world to access and act on important research and evidence

Books have always been very important to William Sutherland. Research and evidence are vital to his work as a conservationist and vital to others in his field. So the Professor of Conservation Biology and Director of Research in the Department of Zoology at the University of Cambridge, was shocked to discover how many academics and community groups across the world were denied access to much of the academic research.

Research that is priced out of reach

When researching his book *The Conservation Handbook*, Sutherland travelled the world, visiting the libraries in the countries he visited. That was when he realised how difficult it was for local conservationists to access research – libraries were often locked or poorly stocked as they could not afford to buy expensive academic books or pay hefty subscription fees. Sutherland said:

“ Books are only accessible to a limited number of people and where there’s the greatest need for conservation, these books are hardest to acquire and hardest to afford.

Giving books away for free

Sutherland wanted to get his research into the hands of people he thought needed it most, so he struck a deal with his publisher – he would forego his royalties, spending the money on distributing free copies of his book. For every book sold, another was sent to a practitioner, free of charge, giving them access to knowledge. A total of 3362 free copies were shared this way.

He said:

“I wanted to make a difference. I want to have an impact on the world and I want the world to be a better place.”

Sutherland did the same with a series of books he edited and set up a website called Conservation Evidence, where he and a team of like-minded academics compile an open access database of the scientific literature.

Academics are paid to be researchers

While acknowledging that some people need royalties from their books, Sutherland thinks research should be accessible to as many people as possible across the globe, not just those in the Global North. He says publishing open access goes a long way to achieving that, and that his work has had much greater reach and impact by making it freely available.

He added:

“If you’re an academic, you’re paid to work. Rather than concentrating on making a small amount of money out of writing a book, why not concentrate on getting it read and making a difference? Because that’s our job.”

Equitable models of publishing

Sutherland has published nine books open access and in 2023, the Conservation Evidence project won the Vice-Chancellor’s 2023 Award for Research Impact and Engagement for the most impactful research at Cambridge University. He is a firm

believer in open access, but says there are challenges that need to be addressed so that everybody can afford to publish, not just those with deep pockets or wealthy universities to fund them.

“ We need to ensure we do not move from a world where only an elite can read the scientific books and journals to a world in which only an elite can publish books and papers due to publishing fees. That is a concern, and we need to make sure we have the solutions.

Jane Winters,
Professor of Digital
Humanities and
Director of the Digital
Humanities Research
Hub, University of
London

Open access enhances the research process

– Jane Winters

Open access is good for research and good for researchers. It encourages scholarly practice, diverse perspectives and interdisciplinary working.

Open access publishing enables academics to disseminate their work to a larger, more diverse audience. It also means academics can access a larger, more diverse range of research materials.

Speculative reading

Jane Winters is Professor of Digital Humanities and Director of the Digital Humanities Research Hub at the University of London. She says humanities research is increasingly interdisciplinary, requiring academics to access research outside their core area. Speculative reading is very important, leading to a richer research experience and outputs, but university libraries and academics often don't have the funds to purchase extra-curricular material.

Winters says:

“The cost of academic monographs in particular is so high that speculative, out of interest reading is unlikely to happen if it requires purchasing a copy of a book.”

When research is freely and easily available, Winters thinks academics are more likely to engage with speculative reading, on the off chance it might be relevant. If it's expensive and hard to access or find, she says they might think it's not worth the effort.

Diversity of thinking

Open access publishing facilitates collaborations with a wide group of people, encouraging the cross-pollination of ideas, experiences and perspectives. It also helps get research known and cited more quickly, raising the profile, awareness and impact of humanities research.

Winters says it's very important that humanities research is accessible to a wide audience, that academics are engaging with and contributing to public debate and helping to shape discourse. She said:

“ In my field, for example – I'm writing about the impact of artificial intelligence on cultural heritage – you want the people who are designing artificial intelligence systems to know about humanities work on bias and ethics. If it's locked away, they're not going to encounter it.

By working and publishing openly, Winters says academics are able to engage with a more diverse set of voices during the whole research process. These voices feed into the research, informing the findings and output.

Benefits to early career scholars

Early career researchers are often advised against publishing open access, with senior academics saying prestige publishing will advance their career more quickly and lead to tenure. But Winters says prestige publishing is not a proxy for quality – open access can be just as good quality.

For a couple of years, Winters was editor of an early career researcher book series called New Historical Perspectives, which does not charge open access costs. She says publishing open access worked very well for them.

“ The early career researchers benefitted enormously from the attention their open access books got. And they were able to cross-promote each other’s work, building a real community around that. It was really effective in career development terms – I think open access is terrific for people early on in their career.

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Participants

Information about researchers interviewed for the case studies, including the publishers with whom they published open access books and edited open access book series are listed in Table 1.

Name	Organisation	Subject area	Publishers
Dr Janneke Adema	Coventry University	Digital media	MIT Press
Emeritus Professor Gwyn Bevan	London School of Economics and Political Science	Policy analysis	LSE Press
Professor Francesca Coppa	Muhlenberg College	Theatre and film studies	University of Michigan Press
Professor Martin Eve	Birkbeck College	Literature, technology, and publishing	Palgrave Macmillan, Stanford University Press, Oxford University Press, Cambridge University Press, punctum books, MIT Press, Bloomsbury, Open Book Publishers
Professor Jean-Paul Faguet	London School of Economics and Political Science	Political economy and decentralised governance	LSE Press, World Bank
Professor Aileen Fyfe	University of St Andrews	Modern history	UCL Press
Dr Elie Gore	University of Manchester	Global political economy, global development, and gender & sexuality studies	University of Michigan Press
Professor Roger Kain	School of Advanced Study	Geography and cartography	University of Chicago Press
Professor Geoffrey Khan	University of Cambridge	Linguistics	Open Book Publishers
Professor Marie Lall	University College London	Education reform and policy	UCL Press
Professor David Luke	London School of Economics and Political Science	Economics and trade	LSE Press

Dr Samuel Moore	University of Cambridge	Digital media and communication	Cambridge University Press, Ubiquity Press
Professor Joanna Page	University of Cambridge	Latin American studies	University of Michigan Press, University of Calgary Press, UCL Press, Open Book Publishers
Professor Matthew Reynolds	University of Oxford	World literature and translation	Open Book Publishers
Professor William Sutherland	University of Cambridge	Conservation biology	Open Book Publishers, Cambridge University Press
Professor Jane Winters	School of Advanced Study	Digital humanities	Springer Nature, Royal Historical Society

Table 1.

Authored and edited open access books

Open access books authored and edited by researchers interviewed as part of this project are listed in Table 2.

Books	Year	Author	Publisher	Subject area
Living Books: Experiments in the Posthumanities	2021	Janneke Adema	MIT Press	Digital humanities and new media
Available at: https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11297.001.0001				
Delhi's Education Revolution: Teachers, agency & inclusion	2022	Kusha Anand, Marie Lall	UCL Press	Education
Available at: https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800081383				
How Did Britain Come to This? A century of systemic failures of governance	2023	Gwyn Bevan	LSE Press	Political science, public policy
Available at: https://doi.org/10.31389/lsepress_hdb				
Vidding: A history	2022	Francesca Coppa	University of Michigan Press	Art, media studies, gender studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.10069132				

Pynchon and Philosophy: Wittgenstein, Foucault and Adorno	2014	Martin Paul Eve	Palgrave Macmillan	Literature, Philosophy
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137405500				
Open access and the humanities	2014	Martin Paul Eve	Cambridge University Press	Humanities
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316161012				
Literature Against Criticism: University English and Contemporary Fiction in Conflict	2016	Martin Paul Eve	Open Book Publishers	Literature
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0102				
Close Reading with Computers	2019	Martin Paul Eve	Stanford University Press	Digital humanities, literature
Available at: https://doi.org/10.21627/9781503609372				
Reassembling Scholarly Communications: Histories, Infrastructures, and Global Politics of Open Access	2020	Martin Paul Eve and Jonathan Gray (editors)	MIT Press	Information science
Available at: https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11885.001.0001				
Password	2020	Martin Paul Eve	Bloomsbury	Critical theory, literary studies, material culture, product design
Available at: https://doi.org/10.5040/9781501314902				
The Digital Humanities and Literary Studies	2021	Martin Paul Eve	Oxford University Press	Literary studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198850489.001.0001				

Warez: The Infrastructure and Aesthetics of Piracy	2021	Martin Paul Eve	punctum books	Cultural studies, media, technology, critical theory
Available at: https://doi.org/10.53288/0339.1.00				
Reading Peer Review: PLOS ONE and Institutional Change in Academia	2021	Martin Paul Eve, Cameron Neylon, Daniel O'Donnell, Samuel Moore, Robert Gadie, Victoria Odeniyi and Shahina Parvin	Cambridge University Press	Publishing and book culture
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108783521				
Theses on the Metaphors of Digital-Textual History	2024	Martin Paul Eve	Stanford University Press	Digital humanities, digital material studies, computing history
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1515/9781503639393				
Decentralised Governance: Crafting Effective Democracies Around the World	2023	Jean-Paul Faguet, Sarmistha Pal (editors)	LSE Press	Government, international development, public policy
Available at: https://doi.org/10.31389/lsepress.dlg				
A history of scientific journals: publishing at the Royal Society 1665 – 2015	2022	Aileen Fyfe, Noah Moxham, Julie McDougall-Waters and Camilla Mørk Røstvik	UCL Press	History of science
Available at: https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800082328				
Between HIV prevention and LGBTI rights: the political economy of queer activism in Ghana	2024	Elie Gore	University of Michigan Press	African studies, health & medicine, health policy & management, gender studies, sexuality studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.12067615				
Seabirds in the North-East Atlantic: Climate Change Vulnerability and Potential Conservation Actions	2023	Henry Häkkinen; Silviu Petrovan; Nigel G. Taylor; William J. Sutherland; Nathalie Pettorelli	Open Book Publishers	Environmental studies
Available at: http://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0343				

The Tiberian Pronunciation Tradition of Biblical Hebrew	2020	Geoffrey Khan	Open Book Publishers	Linguistics, semitic languages, Hebrew
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0163 (Vol.1) https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0194 (Vol.2)				
Improving Basic Services for the Bottom Forty Percent: Lessons from Ethiopia.	2014	Qaiser M. Khan, Jean-Paul Faguet, Christopher Gaukler, Wendmsyamregn e Mekasha (editors)	World Bank	Development studies, economics
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-0331-4				
Creative Multilingualism: A Manifesto	2020	Katrin Kohl; Rajinder Dudrah; Andrew Gosler, Suzanne Graham, Martin Maiden, Wen-chin Ouyang, Matthew Reynolds (editors)	Open Book Publishers	Education, linguistics
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0206				
Myanmar's Education Reforms: A pathway to social justice?	2020	Marie Lall	UCL Press	Education
Available at: https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787353695				
Terrestrial Mammal Conservation: Global Evidence for the Effects of Interventions for Terrestrial Mammals Excluding Bats and Primates	2020	Nick A. Littlewood; Ricardo Rocha; Rebecca K. Smith; Philip A. Martin; Sarah L. Lockhart; Rebecca F. Schoonover; Elspeth Wilman; Andrew J. Bladon; Katie A. Sainsbury; Stuart Pimm; William J. Sutherland	Open Book Publishers	Environmental studies
Available at: http://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0234				
How Africa Trades	2023	David Luke (editor)	LSE Press	Economics and trade, sustainable development
Available at: https://doi.org/10.31389/lsepress.hat				

Event Analytics across Languages and Communities	2025	Ivana Marenzi, Simon Gottschalk, Eric Müller-Budack, Marko Tadić, Jane Winters (editors)	Springer Nature	Digital humanities, natural language processing, media studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-64451-1				
Issues in Open Research Data	2014	Samuel Moore (editor)	Ubiquity Press	Education, science
Available at: https://doi.org/10.5334/ban				
Creativity and Science in Contemporary Argentine Literature: Between Romanticism and Formalism	2014	Joanna Page	University of Calgary Press	Latin American and Caribbean studies
Available at: https://press.ucalgary.ca/books/9781552387320/ as a PDF file				
Science Fiction in Argentina: Technologies of the Text in a Material Multiverse	2016	Joanna Page	University of Michigan Press	Cultural studies, media studies, Latin American studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.3998/dcbooks.13607062.0001.001				
Posthumanism and the Graphic Novel in Latin America	2017	Joanna Page and Ed King	UCL Press	Latin American studies, literature
Available at: https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781911576501				
Decolonizing Science in Latin American Art	2021	Joanna Page	UCL Press	Art
Available at: https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787359765				
Decolonial Ecologies: The Reinvention of Natural History in Latin American Art	2023	Joanna Page	Open Book Publishers	American and Latin American studies, visual arts, environmental studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0339				

Prismatic Jane Eyre Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages	2023	Matthew Reynolds <i>et al.</i>	Open Book Publishers	Literature
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0319				
What Works in Conservation	2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021	William J. Sutherland, Lynn Dicks, Nancy Ockendon, Silviu Petrovan Rebecca Smith (editors, 2018)	Open Book Publishers	Environmental studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0060 (Vol.1, 2015) https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0109 (Vol.2, 2017) https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0131 (Vol.3, 2018) https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0179 (Vol.4, 2019) https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0191 (Vol.5, 2020) http://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0267 (Vol.6, 2021)				
William J. Sutherland, Lynn Dicks, Nancy Ockendon, Rebecca Smith (editors, 2015 2017, 2019)				
William J. Sutherland, Lynn Dicks Silviu Petrovan, Rebecca Smith (editors, 2020, 2021)				
Conservation Research, Policy and Practice	2020	William J. Sutherland, Peter N. M. Brotherton, Zoe G. Davies, Nancy Ockendon, Nathalie Pettorelli, Juliet A. Vickery (editors)	Cambridge University Press	Life sciences, ecology and conservation
Available at: http://doi.org/10.1017/9781108638210				
Transforming Conservation: A Practical Guide to Evidence and Decision Making	2022	William J. Sutherland (editor)	Open Book Publishers	Environmental studies
Available at: https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0321				

Table 2.

Open access book series

Open access book series where the researchers interviewed as part of this project served as series editors and/or general editors for volumes are listed in Table 3.

Editor	Book series	Publisher	Subject area
Roger Kain	History of Cartography For more information see: History of Cartography	University of Chicago Press	Geography, cartography
Geoffrey Khan	Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures For more information see: Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures Open Book Publishers	Open Book Publishers	Linguistics
Jane Winters	New Historical Perspectives For more information see: New Historical Perspectives RHS	University of London Press	History

Table 3.